

used effectively to breed for grain protein (Fig. 1).

We grew 149 breeding lines of upland, lowland-upland derivatives, and lowland lines cultivated at an Ibaraki upland field in 1992. Chlorophyll content averaged 4.39 mg/100 cm² for upland rice and 4.03 mg/100 cm² for lowland-upland crossbred lines, which were significantly

higher than the 3.73 mg/100 cm² for lowland rice.

A negative correlation was observed between chlorophyll content and days to heading ($r = -0.448^{**}$). Early-maturing lines generally had higher protein content than late-maturing lines, although we found early-maturing lines with lower protein content in lowland-upland

crossbred lines (Fig. 2). We think that the low protein content was inherited from their lowland rice parents, although they have upland rice plant type, are tolerant of drought, and resistant to blast. These lowland-upland crossbred rice lines produce grain that is easy to process for rice crackers. The lines are also resources for breeding. ■

Grain quality of rice harvested at different maturities

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Harvesting rice at optimum maturity is important for obtaining high milling recovery and good cooking quality. We grew six commercial varieties in nonreplicated 600-m² plots during the 1989 and 1990 cropping seasons to study the effect of maturity stage on grain quality. The crop was kept flooded. The 50% flowering date was recorded.

Subplots of 6 m², replicated three times, were harvested from 27 to 42 d after flowering (DAF) at intervals of 3 d. Samples were sun-dried and milled 2 mo after harvest using Satake Rice Husking Machine Model THU-35A and Burrows McGill Polisher No. 3. Milled whole grains were cooked in excess water.

Grain maturity stage greatly affected rice quality (see table). We observed high total milled rice and head rice recovery with more elongation and less bursting/curling of grains upon cooking when the crop was harvested at 20-23% moisture. This level coincides with 33-36 DAF in all of the varieties except Basmati 198, which took 39 d.

Head rice recovery was low at both early and late maturity stages. Total milled rice and elongation ratio and bursting/curling upon cooking improved with delay in harvesting date up to 20-23% moisture, after which they leveled off. ■

Effect of harvesting rice at different stages of maturity on grain quality. RRI, Kala Shah Kaku, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan. 1989 and 1990.^a

Days to harvesting after 50% flowering	Moisture at harvest (%)	Milled rice recovery (% of rough rice dry weight)		Elongation ratio on cooking	Bursting/curling upon cooking (%)
		Total milled rice	Head rice		
27	27.8	68.02 c	49.62 d	1.702 d	11.90 a
30	25.3	69.13 b	52.75 bc	1.798 c	10.27 b
33	22.9	70.18 a	54.48 a	1.860 b	9.02 c
36	20.3	70.40 a	54.62 a	1.900 ab	8.38 cd
39	17.9	70.42 a	53.75 ab	1.908 ab	8.27 d
42	15.5	70.28 a	51.87 c	1.913 a	8.25 d
CV (%)	-	0.7	2.7	2.3	6.5
LSD (0.05)	-	0.59	1.71	0.05	0.72

^aMeans in a column followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Relationship of Basmati 370 grain quality to soil and environment

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We conducted a pot experiment to study how soil and environment affect quality attributes and aroma development in Basmati 370. The crop was grown at Daska, a traditional rice-growing area, and Multan, a nontraditional rice-growing area of southern Punjab, during 1989 and 1990 dry seasons. See table for treatments. We evaluated the samples 3 mo after harvest.

Values for kernel length and length:breadth ratio were high in the Daska soil and environment sample (see table). Protein content was about the same across treatments. All samples had intermediate amylose and gelatinization temperature. Elongation and volume expansion ratios upon cooking were highest and aroma strongest in rice from Daska soil and environment. Aroma was

very poor in some samples and absent in the rice from Multan soil and environment.

We can conclude that rice from Daska soil and environment was better in cooked-rice cohesiveness and aroma than were any of the other samples. Aroma is the result of soil, environment, and plant type interaction. ■

IRRN REMINDER

Routine research. Reports of screening trials of varieties, fertilizer, cropping methods, and other routine observations using standard methodologies to establish local recommendations are not accepted. Examples are single-season, single-trial field experiments. All field trials should be repeated across more than one season, in multiple seasons, or in more than one location as appropriate. All experiments should include replications and an internationally known check or control treatment.